

TABLE 1—4-ARYLAZO-1-HYDROXYANTHRACENE

Sl. No.	X	m.p. °C	Absorption spectra				Characteristic frequencies in ir spectra cm^{-1}	Fluorescence spectra in ethanol	
			λ_{max} Ethanol nm	$\epsilon_{\text{max}} \times 10^4$	λ_{max} Acetone nm	$\epsilon_{\text{max}} \times 10^4$		Emission	Excitation
1.	2-nitro	240(d)	495	1.25	490	2.25	1590, 1620	383, 400, 430	338, 350, 370
2.	2-chloro	250(d)	495	6.00	480	6.00	1600, 1640	380, 410, 420	335, 350, 370
3.	3-chloro	223-3(d)	505	4.80	490	5.20	1595, 1620	387, 405, 425	335, 350, 375
4.	4-chloro	275(d)	515	4.00	505	4.08	3405, 1450	385, 405, 425	335, 350, 370
5.	2,3-dichloro	250(d)	485	2.76	470	3.44	1600, 1630	350, 370, 390	313
6.	2,4-dichloro	179(d)	510	1.80	505	2.00	1600, 1620	—	—
7.	2,6-dichloro	198-201(d)	495	3.68	485	4.8	1590, 1620	—	—
8.	4-methoxy	145(d)	530	2.96	525	3.26	1590, 1610	360, 380, 410	340, 360

There was good agreement between % C, H, N found and required.

d = decomposition.

Melting points are uncorrected.

of yellow mercuric oxide¹ followed by reduction to anthracene-1-sulphonic acid² and then fusion with potassium hydroxide to yield 1-hydroxyanthracene³.

Synthesis of 4-arylazo-1-hydroxyanthracene: The diazotisation was carried out in the usual way by dissolving aromatic amine in dilute HCl and adding sodium nitrite solution at 0 to 5°. The coupling was carried out in alcoholic medium. To an alcoholic solution of 1-hydroxyanthracene, aromatic diazonium chloride solution was slowly added at 0 to 5° with constant stirring. After complete addition, the mixture was stirred for 1 hr. The precipitate obtained was filtered and dissolved in potassium hydroxide solution (5%). The solution, after filtration, was acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The precipitates obtained were filtered again and washed with distilled water till the filtrate was free from acid. The precipitates were dried at 40° under vacuum. These were crystallised till a constant melting point was obtained.

The absorption spectra of these derivatives were taken on a Spekol spectrophotometer using 10 mm cell in alcohol and in acetone. The absorption maxima values are recorded in Table 1. The ir spectra were scanned on a Beckmann IR-20 spectrophotometer in nujol mull. The fluorescence spectra (emission and excitation) were taken on a Aminco fluorescence spectrophotometer using alcohol as a solvent.

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Reactions of Arylpropargylthioether : Synthesis of Some 1,6-bis-derivatives of Hexa-2,4-diyne

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WHILE working on the reactions of derivatives of 1,4-dichloro-2-butyne¹ we have synthesized various sulphides, sulfoxides^{2,3}, sulphones^{4,5} and N-alkylanilino derivatives⁶⁻⁸. In continuation of this work we undertook the synthesis of various 1,6-bis-substituted hexa-2,4-diyne. We report here the synthesis of I, II, III, IV, V and VI.

The key compound 1,6-bis-(aryltio)-hexa-2,4-diyne (I) has been prepared by the Glaser oxidative coupling⁹ of arylpropargylthioether¹⁰ with Cu(II)-acetate-in pyridine-methanol (Scheme 1).

Oxidation of I with one equivalent of *m*-chloroperoxybenzoic acid in methylene chloride at room temperature gave a mixture of unreacted disulphide (I, 20-25%), 1-aryltio-6-arylsulphoxido-2,4-hexadiyne (II, 35-40%) and 1,6-bis(arylsulphoxido)-hexa-2,4-diyne (IV, 15-20%). When I was oxidised with two equivalents of the peracid, 78-81% of 1,6-bis(arylsulphoxido)-hexa-2,4-diyne (IV), 8-12% of 1-arylsulphoxido-6-arylsulphonyl-hexa-2,4-diyne (V) and a small

Ia, R = *p*-OH, X = S; Ib, R = *p*-Cl, X = S;
Ic, R = H, X = S; II, R = H, X = -NCH₃.

Scheme 1

amount of III was obtained. The same reaction with three equivalents of the peracid gave a mixture of three components, 40-65% of 1-arylsulphoxido-6-arylsulphonyl-hexa-2,4-diyne (V), 8-20% of 1,6-bis(arylsulphonyl)-2,4-hexadiyne and 10-20% of (IV). Exclusively 1,6-bis(arylsulphonyl)-hexa-2,4-diyne (VI, 87-90%) were obtained by oxidation of I with four equivalents of the peracid (Scheme 2). The pmr spectra of the resulting sulphoxido compounds (III, IV and V) are quite interesting. While the sulphide methylene (I and III) and sulphone methylene (V and VI) appear as sharp singlet at δ 3.50 and δ 4.78, respectively in the pmr spectrum (CDCl₃ solvent and TMS as internal standard), the sulphoxide methylene appear as AB quartet at δ 3.60-3.76, J^{AB} = 15-16 Hz. This can easily be explained as >S=O group has pyramidal configuration and hence these sulphoxido compounds are asymmetric. The magnetic non-equivalence of the methylene hydrogens in an asymmetric acyclic compound has been shown to be mainly due to conformation preference¹¹.

IIIa, IVa, Va, VIa; R = *p*-CH₃;
IIIb, IVb, Vb, VIb; R = *p*-Cl;
IIIc, IVc, Vc, VIc; R = H.

Scheme 2

Experimental

The melting points are uncorrected. PMR spectra were obtained with Varian spectrometer using carbon tetrachloride or chloroform-d₁ as solvents and TMS as an internal standard.

1,6-Bis(aryltio)-2,4-hexadiyne (I): Aryl prop-2-ynyl sulphide (0.02 M) was dissolved in dry methanol (5 ml) and to this was added a solution of cupric acetate (7 g) in a mixture of dry pyridine-methanol (1:1; 100 ml) with continuous shaking at room temperature. After the addition of one-third of the cupric acetate solution, the mixture was warmed on a water bath for 10 min with continuous shaking while the rest of the cupric acetate solution was added dropwise. During this warming, the colour of the solution changed from blue to green. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and poured into ice-cold hydrochloric acid (3 N; 300 ml). This was thoroughly extracted with ether (3 × 100 ml), washed with saturated salt water and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. Removal of solvent gave compound (I).

The same procedure was applied with N-methylanilino prop-2-yne and the product (II) was obtained. The solid products (Ia, Ib and II) were recrystallised from pet-benzene mixture. Yield of Ia 60%, m.p. 66°; Ib 83%, m.p. 93°; Ic 80%, viscous oil; II 82%, m.p. 118°. PMR(CCl₄) in δ (90 MHz): Ia, 2.30(s, 6H), 3.50(s, 4H), 7.10-7.50(m, 8H); Ib, 3.30(s, 4H), 7.15-7.20(m, 8H); Ic, 3.25(s, 4H), 7.05-7.20(m, 10H); II, 2.90(s, 6H), 4.00(s, 4H), 6.70-7.30(m, 10H). Elemental analysis(C, H): Ia Found: C, 74.21; H, 5.56. Calcd. for C₂₀H₁₈S₂; C, 74.53; H, 5.59%; Ib Found: C, 59.60; H, 3.18. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₂S₂Cl₂; C, 59.50; H, 3.30%; II Found: C, 83.24; H, 7.06. Calcd. for C₂₀H₂₀N₂; C, 83.29; H, 6.99%.

1-Aryltio-6-arylsulphoxido-2,4-hexadiyne (III): To a stirring solution of 1,6-bis(aryltio)-2,4-hexadiyne (0.002 M) in methylene chloride (15 ml) at 0-5°, *m*-chloroperoxybenzoic acid (MCPBA) (0.002 M) in methylene chloride (15 ml) was added dropwise over a period of 30 min and stirring continued for 1 hr. The completion of the reaction was tested by starch iodide paper. The mixture was washed by Na₂CO₃ solution (5%) twice and then with saturated salt water, dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and solvent was removed to give a mixture of three components as indicated by tlc. These were separated by column chromatography (silica gel) to give unreacted I 30-35%; III 35-40% and IV 15-20%. The product(III) was recrystallised from chloroform-acetone mixture. Yield of IIIa, 40%, m.p. 77°; IIIb 40%, m.p. 118°; IIIc 35%, viscous oil. PMR (CDCl₃) in δ : IIIa (200 MHz) 2.30(s, 3H), 2.40(s, 3H), 3.55(s, 2H), 3.65-3.75(q, 2H), 7.10-7.60(m, 8H); IIIb(90 MHz) 3.52(s, 2H), 3.60(s, 2H), 7.20-7.49(m, 8H). Elemental analysis (C, H): IIIa Found: C, 70.73; H, 5.26. Calcd. for C₂₀H₁₈S₂O; C, 71.00; H, 5.32%.

1,6-Bis-(arylsulphoxido)-2,4-hexadiyne (IV) : To a stirring solution of 1,6-bis-(arylthio)-2,4-hexadiyne (0.001 M) in methylene chloride (10 ml) at 0-5°, MCPBA (0.002 M) in methylene chloride (15 ml) was added dropwise over 30 min and stirring at this temperature (0-5°) was continued for 1 hr. The reaction mixture was washed with Na₂CO₃ solution (5%), saturated salt water and water successively and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. The solvent was removed to give a mixture of two products as indicated by tlc. These were separated by column chromatography (silica gel) to give IV 78-81% and V 8-12%. The product (IV) was recrystallised from chloroform-acetone mixture. Yield of IVa 80%, m.p. 140°; IVb 78%, m.p. 162°; IVc 81%, m.p. 136°, PMR (CDCl₃) in δ (400 MHz) : IVa 2.45(s, 6H), 3.60-3.76 (q, 4H), 7.32-7.60(m, 8H); IVb 3.15-3.42(q, 4H), 6.90-7.10(m, 8H); IVc 3.62-3.82(q, 4H), 7.56-7.75(m, 10H). IVa gave molecular ion peak (m/e) at 354. Elemental analysis (C, H) : IVa Found : C, 67.63; H, 5.17. Calcd. for C₂₀H₁₈S₂O₂; C, 67.79; H, 5.12%; IVb Found : C, 54.90; H, 3.18. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₄S₂Cl₂O₂; C, 54.68; H, 3.03%; IVc Found : C, 66.20; H, 4.17. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₄S₂O₂; C, 66.25; H, 4.29%.

1-Arylsulphoxido-6-arylsulphonyl hexa-2,4-diyne (V) : To a stirring solution of 1,6-bis-(arylthio)-2,4-hexadiyne (0.001 M) in methylene chloride (10 ml) at 0-5°, MCPBA (0.003 M) in methylene chloride (15 ml) was added dropwise over 30 min and stirring was continued for 1 hr. The reaction mixture was then washed by Na₂CO₃ solution (5%), saturated salt water and finally with water, dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. Solvent was removed to give a mixture of three products as shown by tlc. These were separated by column chromatography (silica gel) to give IV 5-10%, V 40-65% and VI 8-20%. The compound (V) was recrystallised from chloroform-acetone mixture. The yield of Va 60%, m.p. 142°; Vb 40%, m.p. 145°; Vc 65%, m.p. 139°. PMR (CDCl₃) in δ : Va (400 MHz) 2.40-2.50(d, 6H), 3.62-3.74(q, 2H), 4.00(s, 2H), 7.32-7.84(m, 8H); Vc (200 MHz) 3.70 (s, 2H), 4.04(s, 2H), 7.58-8.00(m, 10H). Va gave molecular ion peak (m/e) at 370. Elemental analysis (C, H) : Va Found : C, 64.64; H, 4.35. Calcd. for C₂₀H₁₈S₂O₃; C, 64.86; H, 4.86%.

1,6-Bis-(arylsulphonyl)-2,4-hexadiyne (VI) : To a stirring solution of 1,6-bis-(arylthio)-2,4-hexadiyne (0.001 M) in methylene chloride (10 ml) at 0-5°, MCPBA (0.004 M) in methylene chloride (20 ml) was added dropwise over 20 min and stirring continued at r.t. for 2 hr. VI was then obtained as white solid from this reaction mixture following the work up procedure of compound V. These were recrystallised from chloroform-acetone mixture. The yield of VIa 87%, m.p. 210°; VIb 90%, m.p. 206°; VIc 90%, m.p. 190°. PMR (CDCl₃) in δ : VIa (400 MHz) 2.44 (s, 6H), 4.78 (s, 4H), 7.46-7.82 (m, 8H); VIb (90 MHz) 4.00 (s, 4H), 7.25-7.95 (m, 8H); VIc (90 MHz) 3.90 (s, 4H), 7.45-7.90 (m, 10H). VIa gave molecular ion peak (m/e) at 386. Elemental analysis (C, H) : VIa Found : C, 62.02; H, 4.80. Calcd. for

C₂₀H₁₈S₂O₄; C, 62.17; H, 4.70%; VIb Found : C, 50.42; H, 2.65. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₄S₂Cl₂O₄; C, 50.58; H, 2.81%; VIc Found : C, 60.55; H, 3.67. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₄S₂O₄; C, 60.33; H, 3.91%.

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Bromomethylation Studies in Flavone and Flavanone Derivatives

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IN view of the occurrence of several C-methylated flavonoids in nature, it is important to adopt synthetic methodology for the introduction of methyl group in the aromatic ring. One method to prepare the C-methyl compounds is the reductive dehalogenation of the corresponding halomethyl (chloro- or bromo-) derivatives. The preparations of chloromethyl derivatives of chromones, flavones and 7-methoxyflavanone have been reported earlier¹⁻⁴. No work on bromomethylation of these groups of compounds appears to have been published earlier. The present communication describes the bromomethylation of flavones and